

Relativistic implications on the long-range oscillations of super-spring in a simple harmonic motion

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Abstract

In a general SHM oscillator relativistic correlations usually are not taken into account. In this work I will try to analyze simple harmonic motion when spring constant and/or initial displacement from the equilibrium position is very large. In such cases we need to account for relativistic corrections to the oscillator frequency and also to impose other restrictions to the simple harmonic motion, such as maximum SHM frequency possible for the current limiting conditions.

Approximated relativistic angular speed for SHM

Solving SHM equation using relativistic collinear force,

$$m\gamma^3 x''(t) = -kx(t) \quad (1)$$

one can show that solution takes form,

$$x(t) = c_1 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m\gamma^3}}t\right) + c_2 \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{m\gamma^3}}t\right) \quad (2)$$

From (2) one can infer that relativistic angular speed is in the form,

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m\gamma^3}} \quad (3)$$

with γ being Lorentz factor. Acknowledging that maximum linear speed of SHM oscillator is $v_{max} = x_0\omega$, where x_0 is initial displacement from equilibrium position of spring body, we can expand (3) into :

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{x_0^2\omega^2}{c^2}}}\right)^3}} \quad (4)$$

Solving (4) for ω produces very complex polynomial with many higher order alternating terms, but as usual we can try to assume that lowest degree terms produces biggest effect to the frequency, the rest being just smaller corrections, so in this case approximation to (4) becomes,

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{x_0^2} - \frac{m^2 c^6}{3k^2 x_0^6}} + \mathcal{O}^n \quad (5)$$

with \mathcal{O}^n being higher order correction terms. (5) denotes relativistic angular frequency of SHM oscillator given high spring constant or high initial displacement x_0 .

Comparison of relativistic SHM frequency vs classical one

When we draw chart of $\omega(k)$ for relativistic (5) case and classic one we get this picture for parameters ($m = 10^{-5}kg$, $x_0 = 10^5m$),

Fig (I)

When we draw relativistic chart $\omega(x_0)$, also from (5) relationship, using parameters ($m = 10^{-5}kg$, $k = 1MN/m$) we get picture like that :

Fig (II)

Boundary conditions for SHM angular frequency

Spring natural angular speed

From the Fig II it can be seen that angular frequency reaches peak at some point. This natural frequency can be calculated like that. One needs to calculate derivative equation $\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_0} = 0$ (because at function extreme point value never changes) using (5) frequency expression. Then solve it for a boundary x_0 condition. After that substitute this found spring displacement back into (5) to find out final spring natural angular speed. When doing this one gets

$$\omega_{nat} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{k}{m}}, \quad (6)$$

which in the ideal case should correspond to the classical version of $\sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$, but differs here by $\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}$ factor probably because in relativistic $\omega(x_0, k)$ calculations we have omitted higher order \mathcal{O}^n terms for simplicity. Including them may result (6) approaching standard SHM angular speed. For this additional research is required.

Upper bound of angular frequency

As Fig I shows classical oscillator does not have maximum possible angular speed,- it just tends to infinity as $k \rightarrow \infty$, but relativistic version of angular speed is clearly bounded and does not have such singularity. Taking $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \omega(k)$ of (5) we see that maximum possible SHM angular frequency is ,

$$\omega_{max} = \frac{c}{x_0} \quad (7)$$

and this is perfectly understandable because oscillator mass can't cover distance x_0 faster than a light electromagnetic wave itself, so upper SHM angular frequency is bounded by photon traveling frequency between distance ranges $[-x_0, +x_0]$ up to a factor $\pi/2$.

Relativistic SHM oscillator over-damping

Fig I and Fig II shows SHM does not start to oscillate on all values of x_0, k ,- there's a certain threshold of spring constant and initial spring displacement from which relativistic oscillations starts, otherwise - SHM is over-damped and oscillator periodical movement does not start at all. For finding x_0^{min} threshold from where oscillations are not over-damped anymore, one needs to equate first term under square root of (5) to the second term and solve for x_0 . Doing this we get,

$$x_0^{min} = \sqrt{\frac{mc^2}{3^{1/2}k}} \quad (8)$$

Deeper roots of this lower bound of initial spring displacement must be analyzed separately, but mostly it stems from the fact that spring potential energy at the boundary equates to the spring body total energy-mass. Or in other words,- the bigger capacity of spring to store potential energy relative to the body rest energy mc^2 , - the smaller initial distance we need to induce to produce long range oscillations in relativistic spring which would overcome over-damping conditions.

Conclusions

Using relativistic force which produces collinear acceleration to the spring body velocity, I have approximated SHM oscillator angular speed (5). It was shown that on the relatively small initial spring deflections,- spring SHM angular speed approaches classical SHM oscillator frequency as per (6) expression explained. Relativistic oscillator has maximum angular frequency which is noted by (7). As initial spring displacement gets smaller than x_0^{min} in the long range oscillations,- which is characterized by (8),- relativistic SHM oscillator gets over-damped and doesn't even start to oscillate. (8) is very important since it relates spring body rest energy-mass to the spring potential energy.